

Anglican Missionary Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier's contribution to Udalguri District of Assam

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Abstract

Bodos are one of the important tribal groups of Assam mostly inhabited in the foothills of Bhutan constituted mainly by Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR). Udalguri district is a key hub of Bodo tribe known as Kacharis. The location of Udalguri and the tribal population in the district had been able to attract the attention of the Christian Missionaries from the very initial stage of Missionary activities in Assam. History of the Bodo Christians reveals that several attempts to evangelise the Bodos of Udalguri district had been made by different Missionary groups from the middle of the nineteenth century. But the early flourishing Missionary group in the district was the Anglicans. Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier the forerunner of the Anglican Missionary in the district and was the first to prepare the base for Missionary works in the district. An important tool for evangelism was school education. Company government was also keen to support the Missionaries since the government machinery had hardly able to reach the people in one hand and to bring Bodos closer to government to exploit the opportunity to engage them in tea garden works as labourers. C. H. Hesselmeier was in-charge of the 'Kachari Mission' in the district. He not only opened schools for indigenous tribal groups of the district but at the same time translated prayer books both in Assamese and Kachari language and also published articles in the Asiatic Society journal on the hill tribes of North Eastern Frontier present Arunachal Pradesh.

Keywords Bodo, Kachari, Anglican, Missionary.

Introduction

When we trace the early history of Christian Missionaries in Assam a few names like Cyrus Barkar, Oliver T. Cutter and Nathan Brown of American Baptist Mission comes to our mind. Similarly while searching for the early activities of Christian Missionaries among the Bodos of Assam, two names immediately appear before us. One is Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier and then Rev. Sidney Endle. Rev. C. H. Heesselmeier was the forerunner and predecessor to Sidney Endle. But irony is that very few information about Hesselmeier is available to us. Hesselmeier was the first to build up the foundation of Anglican Mission in Udalguri district. The establishment of British rule in Assam facilitates the appearance of Christian Missionaries in North-East India. In the initial stage, British adopted a policy of non-interference in the religious matters of local people but with the passing of time the need of Christian Missionaries was considered to build up government hold on the multiple ethnic groups of the region. The first requirement of the Christian Missionaries was to fulfill the demands of religious practices of European officials and entrepreneurs, secondly, for spreading education (at minimal cost) in the interior places where government machinery was unable to reach and finally, to pacify indomitable tribal groups particularly the hill tribes of the region. Similarly, reasons for getting focus by Udalguri from the very initial stage of Missionary activities in Assam was the presence of a big market in Udalguri where not only people from Bhutan and Tibet but also from China and a large numbers of merchants from Bengal participated for trading goods. Secondly, the Bodo tribal people known as Kacharis were hard working, generous and liberal. The missionaries were interested to take the advantage of trans-border trade to clear their route to China. Simultaneously, Europeans had seen an opportunity to engage the Bodos in tea gardens as labour to fulfill their labour requirements. Thirdly, the Missionary services became essential in the district with the establishment of a numbers of tea gardens in the foothills of Bhutan. Thus this paper will try to focus on the emergence of missionaries in Udalguri

district and the contributions of Rev. C. H. Hessemeyer to the people of the district which had far reaching consequences in the development of Bodos in Assam.

Aim of study

The main objectives of the study are: (a) to highlight the importance of the emergence of Christian Missionary groups in the Udalguri district. (b) to highlight the dedication and contributions of Rev. C. H. Hessemeyer in the spread of Christianity and education among the Bodos of Udalguri district and preparing the Missionary base for his successors.

Review of Literature

In pursuing study on the Anglican Christian Missionaries in Assam as well as North-East India we come across a good numbers of literatures in the form of primary and secondary sources available in different pockets. There are abundance of government files and reports available in the Assam State Archives and West Bengal State Archive and National Museum. For secondary sources we can go through a good numbers of books and journals available like *Missionary Adventures: A Simple History of the S. P. G.* (1911) by Georgiana M. Forde, *The Kachari* (1911) by Sidney Endle, *A History of the Church of England in India* (1924) by Eyre Chatterton, *Christianity in North-East India: Historical Perspectives* (1983) and *Essay on Christianity in North-East India* (1994) by Frederick S. Downs, *British Administration in North East India* (1985) by Meena Sarma Barkataki, *The Anglican Church in North-East India (1845-1970) A Missiological Reflection* (2002) and *Introduction to the History of the Anglican Church in North-East India* (2009) by E. W. Talibuddin, *History of Christianity in India: Major Themes* (2013) by A Jayakumar, *Boro Jatir Itihas, Bhasa-Sanskriti aru Kristan Missionari* (2011) by Dina Nath Basumatary, *History of Education among the Bodos* (2017) by Satyendra K. Sarmah, *NEIHA Proceedings, XVII Session* (1986), etc. All the above mentioned literatures are important to know about the emergence of English Christian Missionaries in North-East India and the role of Anglican Missionaries in Udalguri district.

Methodology

So far as methodology of the study is concerned, the historical method with empirical study has been adopted. The work has been accomplished through both primary and secondary sources. The primary materials have been collected from Assam State Archive and West Bengal State Archive. The secondary materials have been collected from different libraries, both personal and public, of Assam, Meghalaya and West Bengal in the form of books, journals, magazines, articles etc.

Analysis

Udalguri is the fourth district of the Bodoland Territorial Region located at the juncture of Bhutan, Assam and Arunachal Pradesh. The district is surrounded by Sonitpur, Baksa and Darrang districts from the East, West and South respectively and by Bhutan and Arunachal from the North. Udalguri district was declared in 2003 and formally inaugurated as a district on 14th June, 2004. Till the creation of Udalguri as a separate district in 2003 the entire track was a part of the erstwhile Darrang district. With the occupation of Assam by the British East India Company in 1826, they had created the Darrang district covering the areas of present Darrang, Sonitpur, Udalguri and Biswanath districts. In 1835, the Sadar was shifted from Mangaldai to Tezpur. In 1983, Sonitpur was created as a separate district from Darrang and in 2003 Udalguri district was carved out of Darrang and Sonitpur districts.

Emergence of Christian Missionaries in Udalguri district in the middle of nineteenth century was an important incident in modern period of Assam. The first missionary group that made their venture in the district was the Anglican Missionary. Anglican Missionary came to the district as a supporting agency of British India government to serve the European officials of Tea Gardens of the district. But the primary objective of the Missionaries was to propagate the gospel among the locals particularly the Bodos and other non-Aryan tribal groups. To attain the goal, Missionaries primarily used two weapons namely education and medicine. In every church campus, missionaries had their dispensaries and schools. Medical service was very crucial in this area as because the district was a hot bed for diseases like *cholera* and *malaria*. Secondly, education was important because the district was a tribal dominated area without any means of formal education and because of the vulnerability of the area government initiative failed to reach the area. Missionary initiatives for education in the district was a remarkable happening as there was no scope for education in the district at that time due to lack of proper initiatives from the side of government in the district.

Before the Anglican, the American Baptist Missionaries had made a short appearance in the district. In December 1841, Oliver T. Cutter of Baptist Mission visited Tezpur and realised the need for establishment of schools among the Bodos. In 1941, Bodo chiefs from Udalguri had approach Captain James T. Gordon, Chief Magistrate for establishment of schools in Bodo villages. Accordingly, Gordon urged Miles Bronson of Baptist Mission to provide two school teachers from the Baptist Mission School. The American Baptist mission had made some serious attempts for establishing their hold in the district but because of their multiple engagements in different parts of Assam they achieved little

success in this particular field. The failure of the American Baptist Mission brought to the picture the Tezpur Church Mission Society, an Anglican Mission setup by Captain James T. Gordon from the early part of the second half of the 19th century.[1]

The Anglicans took over a small mission that had been started at Tezpur in 1848 or 1849 by Captain Gordon.[2] Captain Gordon employed two German missionaries of the Basel Mission who had been working in Dacca, C. H. Hesselmeyer and G. Dauble, for the purpose of evangelizing the peoples of Bhutan. When the attempt towards the Bhutias proved impracticable, Missionaries had turned towards the Bodos of Udalguri nearer to Tezpur. In 1850, the Church Mission Society was entrusted with the responsibility to propagate the gospel and the extension of general education among the Bodos in the Udalguri district area.[3] With the passing away of Captain Gordon, the mission faced setbacks as because the Mission was established at his individual initiative. Consequently, G Dauble had joined the American Baptist Mission.[4] But Hesselmeyer didn't give up and continued the evangelical works of Church Mission Society in the mission field in spite of financial hurdles. In 1862, Hesselmeyer and the mission was ordained by the Bishop of Calcutta and placed on Society for the Propagation of Gospel's list as a missionary.

The initial opportunities for establishment of schools appeared before Rev. Hesselmeyer when Captain Francis Jenkins, Commissioner of Assam (1834-61), showed his eagerness to develop closeness with the Bodos of the district to persuade them for tea garden and other works. In 1854, Rs. 50/- per month was sanctioned as grant-in-aid for establishing schools among the Bodo of Udalguri district.[5] Accordingly C. H. Hesselmeyer of the Church Mission Society established three schools in Udalguri for the Bodos and Miris.[6] Jenkins expressed his confidence that for the Bodos in the district the measure would be solely acceptable and gratifying.[7] It was observed that when government officials asked the Missionaries to open schools in different villages, the Missionaries willingly did so as it was useful to work with the government protection and grant for the school. Consequently, education and evangelism went hand in hand in the mission field.

In May 1855, C. H. Hesselmeyer's proposal for establishing three more schools in Bodo villages was approved by the government and sanctioned Rs. 15/- additionally for purchasing books for the schools.[8] Captain Jenkins expressed his satisfaction on the missionary initiatives for substitution of the government schools in the region. He mentioned, "Our Government schools are little adapted to meet the wants of the Cacharees ... mission schools in their own villages I feel confident they will have no reluctance to place their children for instruction." [9] On 18th July, 1855, the Governor General of India in Council, in its Despatch No. 72 gave approval to the grants made to Rev. Hesselmeyer for the Bodos of Udalguri.[10] In 1858, the Government of India sanctioned an additional grant of Rs. 100/- per month to Rev. Hesselmeyer for extending his work among the Bodos and other non-Aryan tribes of the Province. In addition to that the Government extended an additional donation of Rs. 150/- for books.[11] With the outbreak of mutiny in 1857, British government changed the grant-in-aid system to Missionary schools. Accordingly, under new subsidiary system Tezpur Church Mission Society was sanctioned a monthly assistance of Rs. 150/- to open schools to educate the Kacharis, Miris and other non-Aryan tribes of the district under the supervision of Rev. C. H. Hesselmeyer.[12]

In the early part of 1860's, the Society for the Propagation of Gospel (S.P.G.) Mission in Assam observed a good opportunity to extend their field by adopting the financially crippled Tezpur Church Mission Society. Accordingly in 1861, Rev. Robert Bland, Chaplain at Guwahati proposed to the S.P.G. Mission to adopt the Tezpur Church Mission Society but could not materialised. Then George Edward Lynch Cotton, the Sixth Bishop of Kolkata and Second Metropolitan of India had shown his keen interest to adopt Tezpur Mission as part of a scheme, which he had advocated to establish a chain of Mission Centres through the North-East and Eastern parts of the Diocese of Kolkata down to Singapore. In 1862, ultimately the Society for the Propagation of Gospel Mission at Guwahati took over the Tezpur Mission station of Church Mission Society.[13] By this time, the Tezpur Church Mission holding about 50 native Christians, 12 Village Schools and a Normal Class for training of teachers. The normal school had 15 students and the other like in Borigaon had 20, Koriapara-24, Bengbari-14, Barpathar-26, Ratanpur-6, Silputa-6, Tinkuri-5, Sekhar-12, Kalaigaon-22, Samabari-12 and Dalgaon-11 in a daily average attendance.[14]

Rev. Hesselmeyer showed utmost sincerity and dedication as a S.P.G. Missionary in the field and ran the schools efficiently that were under his control. The idea of establishing a mission station especially for the Bodos got its final shape in 1864 with the establishment of the "Kachari Mission." Rev. Hesselmeyer was made the first in-charge of the Kachari Mission.[15] By that time twelve schools were set up in the mission field for the Bodos and others and one for the Miris.[16] In these schools 277 boys received

elementary instructions mainly in Assamese with moderate use of Bengali[17] under the supervision of Rev. Hessemeyer.

Besides establishing schools, Rev. Hessemeyer made extensive tour in the Bodo villages for the spread of the gospel in the district. Rev. F. R. Vallings on November 27, 1865 made an observation on the evangelical technique of the S.P.G. Mission among the Bodos and said, "A system of vernacular schools has been established among the Cacharees of the neighbourhood, and there is a small school at Tezpur. The missionaries spend the cold season in itinerating among the Cacharees." At his initiative the number of local Christians started to grow progressively. In the years 1851 the numbers of local Christians was three, seventy in 1861 and hundred and thirty in 1871.[18]

Hessemeyer learnt Bodo language to deliberate his speech and for the evangelical works. The fruit of Hessemeyer's labour was his translated work- the Common *Prayer Book* in Assamese (1868-69). The book was printed by Gilbert and Rivington in 1871 for the S.P.C.K. He also translated Bible Stories *Dharam Puthi* (1855) and *history of Christian Church* (1861), both the work of Dr. C. G. Barth into the Bodo language.[19] Moreover he had published article on 'The Hill Tribes of North-Eastern Frontier of Assam' in Asiatic Society Journal in 1868. Here he referring the tribes of Himalayan region mentioned, "...Dimasa and Boro, or Lalong, now living in the plains of Assam, they seem to have come in contact with the certain degree of Civilization which effected that change both of feature and habits and customs which is so striking to be beholder".[20]

It is worthy to mention here that in Bengbari Rev. Hessemeyer and his assistant Sidney Endle had established one Church (Bodo Mondoli) in 1865 particularly for the Bodos of Udalguri. It was the first Church dedicated to Bodo community in the history of Christianity among the Bodos of Assam. Later, it became the second headquarter of the Kachari Mission.[21]

On 16th August, 1866, Bishop George E. L. Cotton visited Hessemeyer's normal class, which consisted of 10 Christian boys of different races: two Bodo, two Miri, and the rest were Assamese. The boys expressed their desire to return to their respective villages as Christian Schoolmaster.[22] It was observed that due to frequent famines in Udalguri district, the number of schools as well as students' enrolment under the Kachari mission was decreased.[23]

In the last quarterly letter, Hessemeyer reported that, 'Although there was nothing extraordinary which needed reporting; however, during last three months, every Lord's Day (Sunday) congregation regularly had assembled for divine Worship and every Wednesday afternoon catechetical instruction had been imparted to about seventeen to twenty men and women. Also, there was an adult baptism and a solemnization of a marriage. All pupils of the Normal School had rarely failed attending Morning Prayers.'[24]

Normally, during cold season, Rev. Hessemeyer continued taking long journeys for purpose of preaching in Assamese villages and visiting distant schools which were nine in number with 260 scholars as per the register record. When hill tribes used to come down from their mountain homes to receive the annual subsidy which the Government allowed them and to make purchase, Hessemeyer used to take advantage of their visit and would talk with them hoping that his conversation might help to gain commendable success.[25]

In February 1864, Sidney Endle was deputed from England as the S.P.G. Missionary and joined as an assistant to Rev. Hessemeyer.[26] The joining of Rev. Sidney Endle in Udalguri district gave a new vigour in the works of Rev. Hessemeyer. In continuation of Hessemeyer's efforts Sidney Endle also gave much importance on the growth of education and literature of the Bodos. In 1869, Rev. Hessemeyer left the field for Europe. Subsequently, Sidney Endle was assigned with the independent duty of Chaplain of the tea-planting district of Udalguri along with the charge of the Kachari Mission in the district. In 1871, Rev. C. H. Hessemeyer had breathed his last at Europe.

Findings

From the above discussion we can find out some finding as mentioned below-

1. Originally the field was explored by American Baptist Mission observing the possibility of opening a rout to China but because of ineffective measures the field was ultimately covered by the Anglican Missionaries.

2. Initial Anglican Mission Station was established at an individual initiative of Capt. Gordon and then the field was taken over by the SPG Mission.

3. Engagement of Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier brought momentum among the Bodos of Udalguri district. Under Hesselmeier's supervision, for the first time formal education system was launch in the district as a joint venture of the government and the missionaries.

4. Because of the hard works of Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier, the Bodo language able to get a new direction. He was the pioneer in translation of prayer books into Bodo language.

Conclusion

Services of SPG Mission towards different tribes of Udalguri was an important part of the development of modern education in the district. Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier's dedication and commitment towards the people of the district didn't allow him to leave the field till the last in spite of numerous obstacles and disasters. The major difference of SPG Mission with other Missionary groups of that time in Assam was when all other missionary groups discharged their evangelical works in Assamese language SPG mission continued its works in both the Bodo and Assamese languages. Hesselmeier became the pioneer in this regard and his attempt able to attract the local people leading to growing numbers of local Christians. His path was followed by his successor Rev. Sidney Endle and established the Bodo language by writing *An Outline Grammar of Kachari Language: as spoken in the district of Darrang* and his monograph on Bodos 'The Kachari'. Hesselmeier was the pioneer in regards of introduction of formal education in the district. Hesselmeier had successfully persuaded Capt. Jenkins to provide sufficient grants for establishment of ample numbers of primary schools and one normal school along with special grants for books of those schools. His endeavour led to establishment of the 'Kachari Mission' especially to take care of the matters of the Bodos. His untiring efforts brought colour to the works of Anglican Mission in the district and under the banner of SPG Mission he was able to write the history of Kachari Mission in India. Thus, the name of Rev. C. H. Hesselmeier will remain in golden line in the history of the Christian Missionaries in North-East India.

Suggestions for the future Study

In this field very few works has been done by scholars. Whatever works carried out all are a part of some major works on Missionary activities in North-East India or among the Bodos of Assam. But no specific work is pursuing by anyone covering Missionary contribution and Christianity in Udalguri district. Thus there is ample scope in this field to pursue full-fledged research in this field and there are available sources for the same.

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